

ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation: *Issues on implementation are mentioned in Article as relation between international and domestic law. Moreover, international and domestic mechanisms of implementation have been mentioned.*

Keywords: *implementation, the relation, mechanisms of implementation.*

Аннотация: *Вопросы имплементации затрагиваются в статье как соотношение между международным и внутригосударственным правом. Более того, упоминались международные и внутренние механизмы реализации.*

Ключевые слова: *реализация, отношение, механизмы реализации.*

The new content and forms of integration processes are conditioned by their transition to international economic and market relations. Economic integration creates the need for legal integration, the implementation of international law, in view of which the problem of harmonization (alignment) of the legislation of the member states of the integration association is actualized. Back in the Soviet period, Professor G.V. Ignatenko emphasized the fact of "coupling" legislation with international treaties.

The concept of implementation is one of the most widespread theories of law, mediating a set of measures aimed at recognizing the legal force and organizational support for the implementation of international legal norms within the State. Implementation is the most important component of the effectiveness of international and domestic law. The implementation of the provisions of international law in the parameters of the actual implementation of international law

in individual States is carried out by transforming international legal norms into norms of domestic (national) law.

To this end, legislative measures are being taken in the State to bring national norms into line with the norms of international law, domestic legislative acts (laws, acts of ratification of international treaties) are being adopted, reproducing the norms of international law or regulating their operation on the territory of the State. Since international law does not prejudge all issues related to the implementation of international treaties, they should be settled in domestic law. As R.A. Kolodkin notes, "there are very few laws on international treaties, although they continue to be adopted" International treaties ratified by the Republic have priority over its laws and are applied directly, except in cases when it follows from an international treaty that the publication of a law is required for its application. By signing an international treaty, the State undertakes to ensure its implementation.

A State cannot, referring to the norms of its national law, refuse to comply with an international treaty to which it is a party (article 27 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties of 1969). States are obliged to respect and faithfully comply with the norms of international law: norms of jus cogens; treaties embodying these norms; norms of customary law; general legal principles; binding normative acts of international organizations; certain unilateral acts giving rise to international obligations. At the end of the XIX century, V.P. Danevsky wrote: "International treaties are concluded in order to be executed in good faith". In international legal science, the opinion has been expressed that the direct effect of the norms of international law in the national legal system is due to the special nature of these norms, incorporated, borrowed from international law. In international legal practice, the terms "compliance", "application", "implementation" are used as equivalent (Vienna Convention on the Law of International Treaties of 1969). In official UN documents, decisions of international organizations, in various publications, the term "implementation" (English "implementation" -

implementation, implementation) has become widespread. The implementation of international law is the actual implementation of international obligations at the domestic level.

International law does not require recognition at the domestic level of its primacy and direct action. The choice of the method of implementation of international obligations remains the prerogative of States. International law is predominantly consensual, not imperative. Currently, the implementation of international obligations through the use of the implementation mechanism is predetermined by the requirements of one of the imperative principles of international law - the principle of conscientious fulfillment of international obligations, and in a narrower sense - the principle of *pacta sunt servanda* (treaties must be respected).

This principle is the basis for the interaction of international and domestic law and is implemented through constitutional norms on the place of international law in the legal system of the State. The interpretation of the *pacta sunt servanda* principle presupposes the existence of two interrelated and sequential stages of the implementation of international treaties into national legislation: the stage of expressing consent to be bound by the contract and the stage of execution. In relation to the first stage, the goal is to find out when and in what forms the State expresses its final consent to be bound by an international treaty, while in relation to the second stage, it is to establish by whom and to what extent the execution of treaties is ensured in domestic law and in practice. Legal features of the implementation of the norms of international law and national law.

1. The activity of subjects of national law on the realization of their subjective rights and obligations is a set of organizational and operational measures mediated by law, as a rule, not related to law-making. The implementation of the norms of international law often provides for additional legal measures taken at both the international and national levels. In this regard, the process of implementing the

norms of international law itself falls into two interrelated stages: legal and organizational and operational.

2. In the internal system of law, the State itself creates or authorizes legal norms, gives them an authoritative, binding force and, if necessary, ensures their implementation by the force of state coercion. In international relations, subjects of law, primarily States, create norms of international law in the course of coordinating the wills of these subjects regarding the content of the rule of conduct and recognizing it as legally binding.

3. In the international arena, there is no single centralized apparatus for monitoring the implementation activities of States. States independently monitor the implementation of international obligations. The implementation of a legal norm in its content, together with the emergence of subjective rights and obligations for the relevant person, also represents their implementation in the course of a certain activity, behavior of a subject of international law. International and national mechanisms of implementation The international mechanism for the implementation (implementation) of the norms of international law is presented in the form of a set of conventional (normative) and institutional (organizational and legal) means used by subjects of international law at the international and national levels in order to implement the norms.

1. The Convention mechanism for the implementation (implementation) of norms includes law-enforcement rulemaking, international control, interpretation, law enforcement. For the most part, law-enforcement rulemaking takes the form of concretization, which is of exceptional importance: a high degree of generalization of primary norms can make it difficult to implement them. International control. Among the means known in the history of international law to ensure the fulfillment of international obligations by States (oath, oath, pledge, occupation of territory, surety, guarantees, etc.), international control is a way of verifying compliance with international law. The Institute of International Control is a system of legal norms

established in international agreements, the subject of regulation of which are the relations of States to verify compliance with international legal obligations. Interpretation of acts together with specification can be carried out both at the stage of rulemaking and law enforcement. Law enforcement is an activity culminating in the adoption by States (individually or collectively) or by a competent international body of a legally binding act based on the norms of international law. An example would be a Security Council resolution, a decision of the European Court of Human Rights.

2. The international organizational and legal (institutional) mechanism for the implementation of international law includes States, organizations and bodies (committees, commissions, judicial bodies) whose activities are carried out through negotiations, consultations, meetings, conferences, consideration of issues in conciliation commissions, judicial proceedings. States primarily use negotiations to discuss the implementation of existing norms and to jointly respond to their violations. International bodies (committees, commissions, working groups) are established either on a permanent basis (the Committee for the Protection of Human Rights), or to address a specific issue (the commission of experts). It is possible to speak about the implementation of international legal norms only if the State not only issues relevant legislative acts (changes or cancels existing ones) to implement the norms of international law, but also implements these acts. The opinion of fair. L.H. Mingazova, that "implementation is one of the main prerequisites for the effectiveness of international legal principles and norms" The implementation of international treaties depends on many conditions, including economic, legal, political, ideological, etc.

The state of legislation, its stability and stability, and at the same time the ability to react dynamically to international legal phenomena are the most important factor in the implementation of the norms of international law recognized by the State as binding.

The results of the study of constitutional implementation mechanisms allowed us to identify the following ways of implementing the norms of international law, which are based on the provisions of the constitutions:

a) the criterion of recognition of a monistic or dualistic approach to the relationship between international law and national law;

b) the criterion for the application of the norms of international law, depending on their legal nature: contractual norms and customary norms. Based on this criterion, scientists distinguish 3 categories of implementation mechanisms:

1) constitutional implementation mechanisms that consider only an international treaty as part of national law or the national legal system ;

2) constitutional implementation mechanisms that recognize only for the usual norms of international law the possibility of their application in the national legal sphere;

3) constitutional implementation mechanisms that recognize any norms of international law as part of the national legal system.

From the analysis of the constitutional implementation mechanisms, the conclusion is formulated about the specific ways of implementing the norms of international law in national legislation, which are very diverse. Monistically oriented states are characterized by such a method as a reference, which is divided into 2 types: - general, when it comes to the status of all international treaties (for example, as in the US Constitution) or ordinary norms of international law (the Austrian Constitution); - partial, applied to a specific law containing norms that contradict specific provisions of the contract. Dualistically oriented States are characterized by such a method as incorporation, i.e. the entry into force of an international treaty or custom on the territory of a State by a special law (sometimes it is called an implementing law). Incorporation can be carried out in the form of reception and transformation.

At reception, the implementing law reproduces the content of the incorporated contract without making changes or clarifications to its provisions. During the transformation, the implementation law may clarify, specify the provisions of the relevant international treaty, cancel the effect of old laws if they are in conflict with the international treaty being introduced. The national mechanism for the implementation of the norms of international law of each particular State has features inherent only to it, depending on the peculiarities of the domestic legal system.

At the same time, a number of elements, primarily characterizing its structure, are common to any State.

The structure of the national implementation mechanism includes the following elements:

-legal means enshrined in the national legal order to ensure the fulfillment of international obligations at the national level within the framework of constitutional and legislative mechanisms;

- national law enforcement practice;

- the system of state bodies authorized to implement international obligations;

- organizational means used at the national level to ensure the implementation of the provisions of international law.

The basis of the national mechanism for the implementation of international law is the domestic system of regulatory support: general legal acts, national legal acts. Achieving the goals of implementation into national legislation leads to:

- to increase the level of protection of human rights and freedoms in the state;

- improvement of economic, social and cultural conditions of life in it;

- expansion of the sphere of mutually beneficial and comprehensive cooperation of states;

-strengthening international peace and security, contributing to the prevention of regional and local conflicts and wars.

Thus, at the present stage, implementation is the optimal and rational way to ensure the achievement of these goals by including international norms in the domestic legal system and ensuring its compliance with generally recognized principles and norms of international law, including the protection of human rights.

This circumstance is also accompanied by the fact that international legal norms may "often contain provisions with the ultimate goal of regulating not relations between States (regulating relations between States themselves is a means to achieve the ultimate goal), but relations with the participation of subjects of national law. In this case, it is necessary to "redirect" the norms of the latter, which is achieved with the help of the norms of national law".

International treaties ratified by the Republic have priority over its laws and are applied directly, except in cases when it follows from an international treaty that the publication of a law is required for its application

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